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AIDAInnova

Advancement and Innovation for Detectors at Accelerators
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MILESTONE REPORT

DESIGN REVIEW OF 28 NM RUN

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Abstract:

WP11.2 aims at investigating the use of the 28 nm CMOS node to design the next-generation ICs for particle detectors. In this context, key properties of the technology, such as its radiation hardness, are studied with suitable test structures and IPs in large demand in radiation detection systems, such as front-end amplifiers, ADCs and TDCs are implemented to achieve faster development cycles in future projects.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2024

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Executive summary

CMOS 28 nm has been identified as the next technology node to be used after the 65 nm to implement future advanced integrated circuits for radiation detectors. The technology is well established in the industry, but its use in the context of detector instrumentation still needs to be consolidated. As a first step, the performance of the technology in harsh radiation environments needs to be fully understood. This is necessary in order to deploy design and protection strategies that can optimise its performance in each application. As with any other very deep-submicron process, also the 28 nm is mainly tailored to advanced digital circuits. With a power supply of only 1 V, the implementation of analogue blocks is not trivial, and this is further exacerbated by the additional constraints posed on transistor layout. R&D is thus required to bring this technology to full use in the field. Given its density, the technology is particularly suited to implement novel readout chips for hybrid pixel detectors as well as chips targeting very fast timing and/or very fast data transmission speed. The exploratory studies on the 28 nm node are the subject of the task WP11.2 of AIDAInnova

The deployment of test chips in Multi Project Wafer runs (MPW) to investigate the aforementioned issues and the review of such designs before their submission to the foundry constitute milestone MD45.

1. INTRODUCTION

State-of-the-art ASICs for particle detectors are designed in 65 nm and 130 nm CMOS technologies. There are no immediate concerns about the availability of such technologies, which are very mature for the microelectronics market standard. Nevertheless, the perspective of coping with increased data rate, better time resolution and lower power dissipation encourages the design of ASICs for mid to long-term application in technology nodes with smaller feature sizes. There is a large consensus in the community that 28 nm CMOS should be the next step. This choice stems from several reasons. First, the 28 nm is the last node employing standard planar MOS devices, whereas more aggressively scaled technologies already adopted FinFET. The use of such devices entails more design complexity and a significantly higher mask cost in production. The 28 nm, on the one hand, is already small enough to allow the deployment of very complex digital circuits, a fundamental aspect as the digital part is now predominant also in ASICs for detector readout. The transistor speed is also good enough to allow the implementation of very fast transceivers, which will be a key component in future systems. The technology is now very mature which is an advantage as crucial aspects such as its response to the ionizing and not ionizing radiations that required extensive characterization are expected to remain stable over time. On the other hand, the use of the technology is more complex for both the analogue and the digital design. In analogue design, many new layout rules are introduced that reduce the designers' flexibility in optimizing critical analogue circuits. In digital design, the complexity of digital libraries and Process Design Kit (PDK) require a longer training curve. The use of the technology in the AIDAInnova project is thus exploratory, with the aim of fostering its use in the community. As a first step, small ASICs have been designed and fabricated to address two major items: the effective design of key analogue blocks and the characterization of the technology's radiation hardness. Whenever the application becomes relevant, such as in the design of front-end amplifiers, pixel detectors are targeted as hybrid pixel detectors with smaller feature sizes and better time resolution are expected to be critical for improving the performance of future particle detectors. Two chips containing different test structures have been designed and sent to fabrication in 2022.

2. 28 NM MPW ASIC DESCRIPTION

2.1. FRONT-END FOR HYBRID PIXELS

The first test chip designed by INFN groups explored two different concepts for the pixel front end. The first one contains a preamplifier followed by a continuous time discriminator with a local DAC to trim the threshold and allows the measurement of the signal charge with Time-over-Threshold (ToT). This design is like the one implemented for the RD53 project in 65 nm and aims to compare the performance of similar topologies in two different technologies, thus establishing a benchmark. The second design contains an innovative low-power discriminator with self-offset compensation. The reduced size allows the implementation of a simple two-bit flash ADC directly inside the pixel area. In both cases, the size occupied by the analogue blocks is significantly smaller than in 65 nm, allowing the implementation of smaller pixels (25 μ m x 50 μ m) while leaving significantly more space available to implement complex in-pixel digital circuitry. The chip, shown in Fig. 1, was sent to fabrication in October 2022.

Figure 1: Test chip for hybrid pixel front-end

2.2. SINGLE EVENT TRANSIENT AND TID TEST STRUCTURES

Highly ionizing particles can perturb the node inside a digital circuit, causing fast current and voltage spikes. Such spikes can propagate through the logic, inducing single-event upsets (SEU) that can be detrimental to circuit performance. A specific test structure has been designed that allows the characterisation of the single event transients (SET) produced during circuit irradiation. The developed circuit contains in its core a high-speed delay line whose outputs are captured in a digital memory. The core is thus basically a Time-to-Digital converter (TDC). Therefore, this design also serves as a prototype of a fast, low-power TDC with a small enough area that could be incorporated directly into a pixel front-end cell.

Figure 2: Circuit layout of the test structures to study SET and TID effects

The Total Ionizing Dose (TID) induces cumulative damage that degrades transistor performance, in particular their transconductance. Ring Oscillators are very sensitive to such degradations and are therefore ideally suited to quantify it. A ring-oscillator-based architecture specifically optimised for TID monitoring has thus been implemented. Also, the Ring oscillator serves as a basic building block for the implementation of TDCs. These test structures, shown in Fig. 2, were designed by CPPM, Marseille.

2.3. PIXEL ARRAY

A pixel array containing 432 channels organized in a 36 x 32 matrix has also been submitted. Each pixel contains fast and low-power front-end amplifiers followed by a continuous time discriminator with a 6-bit DAC for threshold tuning. The design targets a high-speed operation in order to provide fast timing capabilities. A jitter smaller than 100 ps for a signal of above 4000 electrons has been anticipated by simulations. The jitter further reduces below 40 ps if the signal exceeds 10.000 electrons. The design, shown in Fig. 3, was carried out by CPPM, Marseille

Figure 3: Pixel array

3. OTHER DEVELOPMENTS

Designs described in section 2 were extensively reviewed during October and November 2022 and reached a full maturity that allows a submission in October 2022 (2.1) and December 2022 (2.2), respectively. Other designs have also been started, in particular, a SAR ADC with low power and 10-bit resolution is being designed by AGH in Krakow

4. REFERENCES

ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
MPW	Multi Project Wafers
TID	Total Ionizing Dose
SET	Single Event Transient